

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

Deliverable: Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

30/04/2021

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. – Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D5.4		
Deliverable Title	Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered		
Due Date	30-04-2021	Delivery Date	24-06-2021
Lead Beneficiary	INNOMINE		
Beneficiaries (part.)	ALTEC, INCITES, RICOH, CITE, INAF, ATHENA		
Editor(s)	Katalin Kovács (INNOMINE)		
Authors (s)	Eva Sciacca (INAF), Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Danai Lampidou (NKUA), Daniel Martinez (RICOH) Javier Ramirez (RICOH), Spyridon Rapsomanikis (ATHENA)		
Contributor (s)	Cristobal Bordiu (INAF)		
Reviewer(s)	Nikos Chondros, Eleni Petra (NKUA)		
Workpackage No	WP5 – Business innovation cases		
Version	V1.1	Stage	Final
Version details	Revision: 859 . Last save: 2021-08-04 , 12:08 Pages: 47 . Characters: 54450. 0		
Distribution	PU	Type	Report
Keywords	innovation management, open innovation, business innovation cases, user involvement		

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Change Record

Version	Date	Description	Editor	Changes
V1.0	24-06-2021	Document version submitted to EC	Katalin Kovács	
V1.1	30-06-2021	Corrected based on the feedbacks received at the mid-term review	Katalin Kovács	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is a project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that

implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 27 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	6
Abstract	7
1. Introduction	8
2. The Concept of the NEANIAS Open Call	9
3. Preparation Activities	12
3.1. Roles of NEANIAS partners.....	12
3.2. Timing of main activities.....	13
4. Project Level Communication	16
4.1. General channels of communication.....	18
4.2. Communication materials.....	24
4.3. Internal communication.....	24
4.4. Target groups and messages.....	25
4.5. Outreach in terms of statistics.....	26
5. Communication Activities on Thematic Levels	27
5.1. Underwater Thematic Area.....	27
5.2. Atmospheric Thematic Area.....	27
5.3. Space Thematic Area.....	28
6. The Submission and Evaluation Process	30
6.1. The main steps of the process.....	30
6.2. The first round of evaluation.....	30
6.3. The second round of evaluation and selection criteria.....	32
7. Conclusions and next steps	35
8. Appendixes	36
8.1. Appendix 1: NEANIAS posts.....	36
8.2. Appendix 2: List of direct mail contacts.....	38
8.3. Appendix 3: SM groups with outreach targeted by innomine.....	41
8.4. Appendix 4: General communication channels of NEANIAS.....	43
8.5. Appendix 5: Banner of the Open Call.....	44
8.6. Appendix 6: Questions of the Application Form.....	44
8.7. Appendix 7: Main criteria for the Scoring of Applications.....	45
8.8. Appendix 8: Interview dates and evaluators - Second round of selection.....	45

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Tables of Figures & Tables

Figure 1: The concept of the NEANIAS Open Call	9
Figure 2: Target groups of the NEANIAS Open Call	10
Figure 3: Innomine's Open Call - Communication Campaign	14
Figure 4: Number of visitors - Innomine's NEANIAS webpage	18
Figure 5: Website visitors per country	19
Figure 6: Open Call Video Main Page	22
Table 1: The Members of the Open Call Evaluation Board	12
Table 2: Number of views on Innomine's post about the Open Call.....	17
Table 3: The Number of Applications per Thematic Sector – First round of Open Call	30
Table 4: List of applicants – selected in the first round	31
Table 5: List of applicants - not selected in the first round	31
Table 6: Business criteria of Open Call applicant’s evaluation	32
Table 7: Technical criteria of Open Call applicant’s evaluation	33
Table 8: The winners of the First Open Call	33

Abstract

NEANIAS Project partners have been driving the co-design and delivery of 10+ innovative thematic services, derived from the state-of-the art research assets and practices in hopes of overcoming emerging challenges; like bringing together actors from several disciplines (astrophysics, planetary, ocean, climate, archaeology, geology, computer science and more) to expand the vision of the project on business cases as a result of Open Innovation Calls. There are two Open Calls organised in the framework of the NEANIAS project, to invite potential external end-users in testing, and integrating NEANIAS services of all thematic sectors, and provide valuable feedback for NEANIAS partners on creating new business perspectives. The Open innovation method utilised in NEANIAS considers the target thematic areas of the services, including Start-ups, Established private companies from diverse industries (SMEs / Multinationals), and Groups of individual researchers / innovators of up to 3 members. As a result of the intense activities, the First Open Call is closed successfully, with 21 applications, who applied to utilize and integrate NEANIAS services to create new business cases. Organizing and implementing the First NEANIAS Open Call was a complex process, and this deliverable summarizes all preparation and implementation activities, including communication.

1. Introduction

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. NEANIAS is a project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. NEANIAS drives the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities. NEANIAS Project partners has been developing 10+ novel services, and NEANIAS drive the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: **Underwater** research, **Atmospheric** research and **Space** research, each engaging **multitudinous** academic and business groups, **numerous** researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

European Start-ups often face difficulties in the early phases, mostly because of the lack of high-quality infrastructure and human resources available to test and efficiently develop their technology. NEANIAS aims to provide technical support to tackle these challenges. The purpose of this Open Call is to spark and support the development of a wide variety of innovation projects with business perspectives, by providing novel services created in the framework of the NEANIAS project, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and contributing to advance research and innovation in Europe. The overarching goal was to build up and strengthen the European innovation community by identifying and supporting innovative projects with novel services developed in the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research fields. Innovation in this scope may refer to (a) new operation models for existing services, that can exploit NEANIAS resources (b) improving existing services utilizing NEANIAS offerings to increase their overall offering (c) brand new services inspired by NEANIAS offerings (d) new services in need offerings such as NEANIAS and EOSC ones, and many more. To boost the development of new business opportunities and accelerate the onboarding of external users into the project, NEANIAS has organized its first Open Call for Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Science initiatives. The first Open Call was launched on the 8 February 2021, 9:00 CET and was closed on the 9 April 2021, 23:00 CEST.

This deliverable summarises the Open innovation concept of NEANIAS with special attention on the aspect of user-involvement through the Open Calls. It also gives an overview on the preparation activities of the open call, the intense communication activities, and the selection process with the results.

2. The Concept of the NEANIAS Open Call

The aim of WP5 – Business innovation cases, is about fostering business innovation around the NEANIAS Service offerings, and provide support for business cases, which are derived from the open innovation calls, access and evaluate business cases by their end-users and support building of innovation capacities. The NEANIAS Open Call is implemented within WP5, Task 5.3 Open calls for innovation [M13-M24].

In the framework of this task there are two open calls to be launched, with the aim to build up an innovation community, especially focusing on external community which includes the relevant stakeholders of each thematic sector.

In the framework of organising and implementing the Open Call, NEANIAS partners are looking for applications from Companies and Groups of individual researchers, for utilising Atmosphere, Underwater and Space services by validating/developing their novel technologies. The applications were evaluated based on business and technical criteria. The business criteria included the business potential and added value of the project for NEANIAS partners, while the technical criteria included criteria on novelty, exclusivity, technical excellence and industrial relevance and feasibility of the given concept.

Described by Figure 1, the aim of the NEANIAS Open call is to find innovative projects and provide support for them by utilising the human resources and high-quality infrastructure of NEANIAS.

Figure 1: The concept of the NEANIAS Open Call

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

The reason is that European Startups, research groups and early-stage researchers often face difficulties in conducting research of good quality, in the early stages due to the lack of high-quality human research. They are missing these resources to strengthen their innovation potential. This is the reason they also need support in testing and in utilising NEANIAS services.

Figure 2: Target groups of the NEANIAS Open Call

The main target groups of NEANIAS are start-ups, established private companies from diverse industries (SMEs / Multinationals), groups of individual researchers or innovators of up to 3 members. The reason of targeting these groups is to represent a diversified field of research and innovation, which might use the services of NEANIAS with added value to apply. NEANIAS aims to foster the advancement of interdisciplinary research and innovation, therefore by targeting diversified target groups NEANIAS partners expect the utilisation of NEANIAS services with a high innovation potential.

By submitting their application, the applicants agreed that once their proposal will be selected, both parties will sign an NDA, and take all confidentiality measures into account. The evaluation of applications was made by NEANIAS experts and was based on NEANIAS criteria and the overall scope of the project. The applicants should have accepted, that there was no possibility to appeal against the decision made by the NEANIAS evaluation board on the selected projects. The applicants should have also declared that the project they were submitting has not received any EU or Government funding, as no double-funding is accepted by the NEANIAS board, in align with the European rules.

NEANIAS experts support the selected applicants by providing them access to their infrastructure and also let them utilise the services of NEANIAS. The services provided by NEANIAS include providing the services for an approximately three months for the selected applicant from the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space thematic fields. NEANIAS aims to provide special attention to the business opportunities behind the applications, to provide support in the creation of a Proof of Concept (POC) and its

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

evaluation from a technical and business point of view. The support on business development, depending on the specifications of each project includes providing opportunities in networking, for example, intros to corporates, companies, investors, and other business stakeholders, and provide access to a wide user group developed in the NEANIAS project. The selected applicants might receive support from a pan-European network of experts and be linked to the NEANIAS community.

The selected projects will be promoted through NEANIAS channels. As a result of this support, the added values of NEANIAS services will be communicated together with the advancement of the applications. NEANIAS communication experts will create professional blog posts and targeted social media messages. Besides supporting networking, each project will be evaluated individually to identify their business potential and provide them business coaching, business development support to reach their goals and exploit their business potential. The support includes a so-called innovation case implementation support, including the already mentioned business potential analysis, mentoring, and guiding the applicants on utilizing the services of NEANIAS with the highest business potential. The technological support of NEANIAS is therefore backed by a business support process implemented by WP5 and WP9 experts in parallel. At the end of the support the case report will include the services provided by NEANIAS experts, including business and technical services. The main elements of providing NEANIAS Services:

1. Project abstract creation
2. NDA signing
3. Proof of Concept (POC) implementation (3 months)
4. Proof of Concept (POC) evaluation (1 week)
5. Case report (1 week)
6. Optional additional support and extension period

In alignment with H2020 rules, the list of eligible countries are described in [Annex A](#) of the Work Programme. A number of non-EU/non-Associated Countries that are not automatically eligible for funding have made specific provisions for making funding available for their participants in Horizon 2020 projects. The details of eligibility were clearly described to the applicants by sharing with them the [Online Manual](#), and specific questions of the applicants were clarified by answering their individual requests.

3. Preparation Activities

3.1. Roles of NEANIAS partners

The first Open Call was launched on the 8 February 2021 and was closed on the 9 April 2021. NEANIAS Partners conducted a centralised effort in terms of communication and provided all information about the opportunity to urge relevant parties to apply for the Open Call.

Target groups, reached out by NEANIAS experts:

- Start-ups
- Established private companies from diverse industries (SMEs / Multinationals)
- Groups of individual researchers / innovators of up to 3 members.

The added values of NEANIAS were communicated by each Thematic sector representatives to their target audience. The open call was organised in a way that it takes all geographic areas into consideration within the scope and geographical coverage of Digital Innovation Hubs. The communication and organisation of the open call was very intense, by using all social media channels, targeted messages to reach out to the target audience of each thematic sectors. The task was led by Innomine Group, a Digital Innovation Hub, based in Hungary with a wide coverage all over Europe, a well-known innovation management expert in the NEANIAS ecosystem. The communication activity was led by RICOH, WP10 leader, based in Spain with the role to take the lead and coordinate all communication activities within the project. RICOH and Innomine both analysed the channels of communication and identified the main groups of communication with regards the open call. They were the main partners responsible for organisation and communication, however each NEANIAS Partner contributed significantly to the implementation of the Open Call. On the one hand their role was to participate at meetings and provide their feedback from technical and business point of view on the main pillars of the Open Call concept. On the other hand, their role was to mobilise their network and to have an active role in communication and to find potential applicants from their professional network.

NEANIAS partners set up an Evaluation Board, whose role was to provide scoring for the applicants and assign NEANIAS experts, who are responsible for evaluating the projects and to conduct the interviews. The members of the Evaluation Board:

Table 1: The Members of the Open Call Evaluation Board

Name	Org.	Role in NEANIAS
Eleni Petra	NKUA	PM - Leader of the Board
George Kakalettris	CITE	TM - Leader of the Board in PM absence
Nikos Chondros	NKUA	WP1 Leader
Paraskevi Nomikou	NKUA	WP2 Leader

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Spyridon Rapsomanikis	ATHENA	WP3 Leader
Eva Sciacca	INAF	WP4 Leader
Ugo Becciani	INAF	WP4 Leader Deputy, User Board Leader
Katalin Kovács	INNOMINE	WP5 Leader Deputy
Gábor Vicze	INNOMINE	WP5 Leader
József Kovács	SZTAKI	WP6 Leader
Georgios Papanikos	CITE	WP7 Leader
George Papastefanatos	ATHENA	WP8 Leader
Ioannis Neokosmidis	INCITES	WP9 Leader
Theodoros Rokkas	INCITES	WP9 Leader Deputy
Stergios Kokorotsikos	EUNICE	Partner representative
Ricardo Vitorino	UBIWHERE	Partner representative

3.2. Timing of main activities

The Open Call Implementation process was divided into three phases. *The first phase* included the preparation activities prior to the launch of the Open Call (8 February). *The second phase* of the Open Call included the preparation and communication activities focusing on the Open Call Webinar, taking place on the 17 March. *The third phase* of implementing the Open Call was focusing on collecting applications and providing advice for potential applicants in creating a successful proposal.

In the first phase, Innomine Group, the WP5 and Task 5.3 leader organised regular meetings to conceptualise the Open Call and foster the communication activity. The date of these regular meetings were: 09 February 2021, 25 February 2021, 09 March 2021, 19 March 2021, 19 April 2021. The main topic of these meetings was conceptualising the conditions of the Open Call and evaluating the communication materials, discuss the main messages of communication and the target groups, actions of communication. Innomine prepared the main documents of the Open Call and shared it with all NEANIAS partners. The main Open Call texts and documents were:

1. Open Call Announcement including the conditions, eligibility criteria and context of the Open Call. The final version was ready by the 1 February 2021.
2. Open Call Implementation Details and Guide for Applicants: this document provided a detailed description about the aims of the call, the detailed conditions, the process, and the expectations from the applicants. The final version of this document was ready on the 4 February 2021.

3. The Application Form including the questions from the applicants were created also by Innomine and was ready already on the 15 January 2021.
4. The NEANIAS Open Call Evaluation Criteria was created by Innomine and was shared and agreed by NEANIAS partners. The criteria were created on the 13 January 2021.

In the second phase there was an intense communication campaign specially to target the audience of the Open Call and invite them to participate at the Open Call Webinar, taking place on the 17 March 2021, at 15:00 CET. To invite participants to the Webinar, Innomine conducted a very intense communication activity, including an intense activity in terms of social media channels, as well as conducted a direct mail campaign targeting the partners of Innomine and other potential associations (e.g., PhD associations) who might be interested in the Open Call. The main element of the campaign is depicted by Figure 3:

Figure 3: Innomine's Open Call - Communication Campaign

Similarly, to Innomine's concept, especially the WP leaders of each thematic sector conducted intense communication activity by inviting their partners, students to participate at the webinar to learn more about the added values of NEANIAS services, and of NEANIAS in general, and specifically to the area they are working on. As a result of the intense communication activity of Innomine, RICOH and all Partners there were altogether 97 registrations for the Webinar, of which finally 70 attended at the Webinar.

In the third phase of the communication activities the webinar participants were especially targeted by direct mails and project partners reached out to them through their channels to convince them to submit their application.

As a result of the intense communication and wide outreach of Atmospheric, Underwater and Space experts, altogether 21 applications arrived, indicating, that they are intended to utilise and integrate NEANIAS services in their project.

As a result of the active work of the Evaluation Board, the projects were selected for interviews with NEANIAS experts. The selected applicants in this phase will have to show strong reuse of NEANIAS offerings and valid sustainability potential.

As the main aim of the Open Call was to find and reach out to the target audience of the project, the communication activities were very intense. The communication activities were twofold. **The project level communication** was managed by RICOH and Innomine with their combined effort reached out to a wide audience, presented the added values of the Open Call, and reached out to all thematic fields.

The thematic level communication was led by WP2, WP3 and WP4 leaders, representing the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space thematic sectors.

4. Project Level Communication

As for Innomine's social media activities, in the framework of WP5, in the process of promoting the NEANIAS Open Call, Innomine created a targeted campaign for specifically relevant Facebook and LinkedIn Groups in the three thematic sectors – Underwater, Atmospheric and Space. The private and public groups were tracked by NEANIAS Partners and were listed in one excel spreadsheet where posting activity was tracked. Once the social media groups were found and the organizers were able to infiltrate the groups – weekly posting and promotion of the NEANIAS project and Open Call ensued. Since the 'reach' meaning amount of group followers in each respective group is very high, so one post could and did make a powerful impact.

Altogether, **10** LinkedIn groups were sourced and contacted, with overall potential reach being **66,810** people/members; and **16** Facebook groups were sourced and contacted, with overall potential reach being **239,716** people/members. The social media (SM) groups varied in thematic fields, spanning / covering all three – Atmospheric, Space and Underwater. The main message of the posts introduced the NEANIAS project as a whole and promoted the Open Call.

The LinkedIn Groups, in which the Open Call was posted/promoted:

- International Society of Intelligent Unmanned System
- The Society for Underwater Technology (SUT)
- National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
- Institute for Marine and Atmospheric research Utrecht (IMAU)
- Tech Experts - Security, Software, Cloud, IoT, Robotics, A.I., Finance, Health, Space & Science
- Future Engineers Innovators & Innovations Science Technology Art Automotive Engineer Aerospace Space
- Space Science and Astrophysics
- Women in Aerospace Europe
- EU Sustainability Public Affairs (Brussels)
- Horizon2020 - H2020 - HorizonEurope

The Facebook Groups in which the Open Call was posted/promoted:

- Horizon 2020, EU Funding & Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
- Underwater Robotic Research Group (URRG)
- Space Research
- Space Research 2
- Space EU
- National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
- UTeM Underwater Technology Research Group (UTeRG)
- HORIZON: the EU Research & Innovation magazine

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

- ISRO Science and Technology
- UKM Atmospheric Chemistry and Air Pollution Research Group
- UTRtek - Underwater Technical Research Tek Diving
- Foundation for Underwater Research and Education
- SPC Underwater Research Society (SURS)
- Smart Cities Trends
- Smart Cities
- ASEAN Smart Cities Network

The major social media platforms used were Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn. The most popular amongst NEANIAS followers being Twitter then Facebook and LinkedIn. Support from partners via shares/re-tweets was constituent and flawless – usually NEANIAS project social media accounts and Innomine would re-share/re-tweet each account post in support, as well as consortium members and partners.

As for the direct mail campaigns, Innomine targeted international groups, associations, and networks, for example the European University Association, the International Association of Universities, and in general umbrella organisations which helps NEANIAS to reach out to students, or potentially to start-ups to find applicants for the Open Call. Besides the networks, smart city groups, and companies dealing with developing space, atmospheric or underwater products were contacted directly.

The direct mail campaigns were done before the Open Call Webinar to convince the target group representatives to participate and learn more about the opportunity.

Innomine, as part of the NEANIAS Open Call, organised targeted SM and direct mail campaigns and mobilised the SM channels. Its activity generated interest and applicants for the Open Call. On average, the company posted on its SM channels **2-3 times a week**, with more frequent posts closer to the Open Call deadline. Innomine created a dedicated NEANIAS project page on its website which also brought many page views directing viewers directly to the NEANIAS project website. The links on the webpage directed all traffic to the Open Call page. The dedicated Innomine project page also had a pop-up on the company's main homepage, which caught visitors' eyes right away. The impact was great, since almost **400** visitors viewed the dedicated NEANIAS page throughout the campaign.

The result of the social media campaign created buzz, promotion, and overall major visibility for the NEANIAS project. The overall statistics for each month can be found on Table 2 below:

Table 2: Number of views on Innomine's post about the Open Call

FACEBOOK		TWITTER		LINKEDIN	
MONTH	VIEWS	MONTH	VIEWS	MONTH	VIEWS

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Jan	38	Feb	2,359	Jan	40
Feb	1,228	March	6,730	Feb	374
March	1,391	April	894	March	303
April	65	May	1,521	April	147

Innomine Website – Google Analytics

As mentioned, Innomine has created its own Open Call website, which served as a back-up, in case of technical problems with the main webpage, and Innomine aimed to channelise its visitors to the Open Call website to collect further applicants. From Feb to April altogether **532** sessions were reached, with over **340** New users/visitors. The average read-through rate / time spent on the webpage 1minute:38seconds.

Figure 4: Number of visitors - Innomine's NEANIAS webpage

4.1. General channels of communication

The main communication channels that have been used to disseminate the announcement and development of the 1st NEANIAS Open Call have been:

Website: The NEANIAS website (<https://www.neanias.eu/>) is the main communication method of the project, serving as an interface with the collaborators (internal and external) and unifying all the information related to the project (objective, results, participants, events, publications, etc.). The Open Call has been a capital event

of the project and has had a wide impact on the website. The impact was worldwide as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 5: Website visitors per country

The Open Call had a banner in the home page to easily notify the visitors about the event. In addition, a specific section, quickly accessible from the home page, addresses the visitors to get all the details about the Open Call. The section has been updated wherever necessary. This webpage can be reached through this link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/open-call>.

This section offered all the information, (the services provided for the selected applicants, the purpose and background of the Open Call, the selection and execution processes, the eligibility criteria and conditions, the link to NEANIAS YouTube channel with a video presentation, all the information about the dedicated webinar, a shortcut to subscribe and apply, some connectors to our social networks and data of contact, and more).

Many articles were produced; illustratively, it is worth highlighting:

Articles: 5 articles have been published in the website related to the Open Call on 12-21-20, 02-02-21, 03-03-21 and 2 articles on 03-15-21.

- News: it has been published 7 notes related with the Open Call on 12-21-20, 02-02-21, 02-18-21, 02-23-21, 03-05-21, 03-17-21 and 03-18-21.
- A specific banner about the Open Call, published on 12-22-20.
- A specific Website section for the Open Call, initiated on 02-01-21.
- Events: newsworthy information about the Open Call event, published on 02-02-21, 03-05-21 and 03-17-21.

The website also counted on RSS (Really Simple Syndication) service that allowed users and applications to access updates to NEANIAS website in a standardized, computer-readable format in order to be updated with any news related to the Open Call.

Twitter:

Twitter is the main social network used by NEANIAS to transmit communications and news related to the project, both to organizations and to individuals. The objective is not only to communicate newsworthy events, but also the evolution and the day-to-day of the project.

For the Open Call event has been published the following tweets:

- A header tweet was pinned on 02-02-21, with great impact on the media (https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1356522108311007233) with more that 9000 impressions and more than 400 engagements.
- 3 tweets about Open Call Webinar on 03-17-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1372194912523972619 with 643 impressions and 19 engagements,
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1372187992631152642 with 917 impressions and 43 engagements and
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1372139939568189444 with 970 impressions and 6 engagements.
- One tweet about Open Call Webinar on 03-16-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1371746375579410436 with 2,495 impressions and 29 engagements.
- 2 tweets about Open Call Webinar on 03-13-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1370793582781730816 with 665 impressions and 22 engagements and
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1370794407721570305 with 336 impressions and 6 engagements.
- One tweet about Open Call Webinar on 03-12-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1370416326536232962 with 2,608 impressions and 29 engagements.
- 2 tweets about Open Call Webinar on 03-05-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1367879005232316422 with 662 impressions and 28 engagements and
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1367879643680956422 with 326 impressions and 12 engagements.
- One tweet about Open Call presentation on 03-03-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1367082392725426178 with 470 impressions and 31 engagements.
- One tweet about Open Call presentation on 02-10-21:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1359546062055354368 with 1,221 impressions and 42 engagements.
- One tweet about Open Call presentation on 12-22-20:
https://twitter.com/Neanias_eu/status/1341411513899376655 with 1,036 impressions and 41 engagements.

Moreover, a crossed support policy was promoted with other projects and relevant players in order to maximize the visibility of our Open Call from other accounts.

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Facebook:

Facebook is the second most used social network by NEANIAS. It allows not only the dissemination of messages and news such as Twitter but also to establish interest groups with mutual monitoring that exponentially increases the dissemination activities of the project.

NEANIAS project has published about the Open Call these posts:

- A pinned post on 02-02-21 with 750 people reached, 106 engagements and 12 likes.
- 2 posts about Open Call Webinar on 03-17-21 with 110 people reached, 19 engagements and 15 likes and 80 people reached, 8 engagements and 4 likes respectively.
- One post about Open Call Webinar on 03-05-21 with 435 people reached, 33 engagements and 10 likes
- One post about Open Call Video on 03-03-21 with 98 people reached, 17 engagements and 7 likes.
- One post about the publication of the Open Call in the NEANIAS Newsletter on 02-10-21 with 89 people reached, 12 engagements and 10 likes.
- One post about Open Call Presentation on 01-19-21 with 521 people reached, 34 engagements and 9 likes.
- One post about Open Call Presentation on 12-22-20 with 86 people reached, 8 engagements and 6 likes.

In addition, interactions were carried out with the different Facebook groups to announce the Open Call and resolve doubts or questions about the process.

Specifically, the following groups were interacted with:

- NEANIAS Group
- Scientific Research Papers & News
- Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research
- Horizon 2020, EU Funding & Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
- EU Projects - partners & participants
- European Scientific e-Journal
- Centre for Maritime Archaeology
- Smart Cities
- HorizonEurope
- Geospatial analysis
- OPEN CALLS
- OpenAIRE
- European Research Council
- EUROLABO: EUROPEAN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- European Funding Grants (H2020, EIT, Interreg etc.)
- HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
- Horizon Community

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

LinkedIn:

LinkedIn is a social network focused on the professional field, widely disseminated in the business and research environment.

NEANIAS Project also has created a dissemination group on this social network (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13786081/>), where the following posts related to the Open Call have been uploaded:

- 2 posts about Open Call Webinar on 03-17-21 with 2 likes.
- One post about Open Call Webinar on 03-05-21 with 2 likes.
- One post about Open Call Video on 03-03-21 with 1 like.
- One post about Open Call publication in Neanias Newsletter on 02-10-21 with 3 likes.
- One post about Open Call Presentation on 01-19-21 with 5 likes.
- One post about Open Call Presentation on 12-22-20 with 3 likes.

YouTube:

YouTube is the main platform for the dissemination of videos, both informative and professional. The NEANIAS project has created a dissemination channel on the YouTube platform to publicize the main events and milestones of the project.

The Open Call has been one of the main events of the project, that is why a video has been uploaded to the YouTube channel explaining the objectives and the main results of the same.

This video presentation (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I5qeQn57fLQ&ab_channel=NEANIAS_EU) was uploaded on 02-23-21 and till now has 170 views.

Figure 6: Open Call Video Main Page

The video was promoted from all our social networks.

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Webinar:

In order to explain to the participants, the objectives and expected results of the Open Call, a Webinar was organized on March 17, 2021, attended by 60 people. The webinar was strongly promoted from all our social networks.

E-mail address:

Although the project has an e-mail account, an additional e-mail address was created to particularly attend the communication needs related to the Open Call. It was promoted too to resolve any doubt or answer questions, both to attendees and to people who could not attend the Webinar. The address is OpenCall@neanias.eu.

Newsletter:

The NEANIAS project periodically publishes a newsletter that it sends to its contacts to inform them of the main milestones of the project. Since the Open Call is an important milestone of the project it was already announced in the newsletter No. 2 of February 10, 2021. We also produced a dedicated newsletter, No. 3 released on March 15, 2021, where the Open Call was explained from its different perspectives: space, underwater, atmospheric, business, innovation, among others.

- **Direct contacts & meetings:**

One of the main communication and dissemination mechanisms of the NEANIAS Project is the network of personal contacts that has been woven through attendance at meetings and events and the sharing of contacts between people involved in the project.

This network of contacts is currently widely extended in the European scientific and innovation ecosystem, with more than 180 contacts of people and organizations.

These contacts were targeted by published newsletters, through them and through direct personal contacts they were informed about the call.

EU projects' ecosystem:

The NEANIAS project has been integrated into the European scientific and innovation ecosystem by creating relationships with projects related to the object of the NEANIAS project or with the European project development environment itself.

Currently the NEANIAS project is integrated into the following groups:

- Blue Cloud and Trust IT Network
- HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
- European Research Council
- Horizon Community
- Horizon 2020, EU Funding & Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
- OpenAIRE

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

- OPEN CALLS
- HorizonEurope
- EUROLABO: EUROPEAN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- European Funding Grants (H2020, EIT, Interreg etc.)
- EU Projects - partners & participants
- Business innovation and R&D
- Geospatial analysis
- European Scientific e-Journal

The integration in these groups is a symbiotic relationship in which the main milestones of the projects are disseminated in a cross way. In this context, the NEANIAS project has used its integration in these groups to disseminate the call, the objectives and the results of the Open Call.

4.2. Communication materials

The main communication materials that have been generated to inform (through the commented channels) the target ecosystem of the NEANIAS project have been:

- **Presentation:**

The first content created was the presentation of the Open Call, explaining its objective, the expected results and the conditions of the call. This presentation was adapted to different formats (teaser, e-mail, brief note, post, etc.) to inform through the different channels previously indicated.
- **Different templates for target groups:**

Templates have been generated for the type of communication format (presentation, e-mail, press release, post, etc.) to report on each of the Open Call steps (presentation, call, webinar, results, etc.) to the ecosystem of interlocutors of the NEANIAS project.
- **Material for the webinar:**

The webinar that was organized to inform about the Open Call was a very important event for its development, so abundant documentation was developed both for the announcement of the Webinar and for its realization. Additionally, some material and templates were produced to help promote this event. The activity was carried out in close coordination with thematic sectors and other WPs to find the best message to address to any audience.
- **Banner:**

The banner has been a graphic resource that has served both to illustrate the information about the Open Call in the different communication channels used, as a reminder of the event on the website and in the different social networks of the NEANIAS Project.

4.3. Internal communication

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

The Dissemination and Communication team developed a task of internal communication and engagement in order to help the NEANIAS partners to promote the event and attract as many skilled and interested applicants as possible. This task was designed in close coordination with WP5-Innovation and WP1-Management. The internal channels and meetings were used to promote, explain, and engage the whole NEANIAS team.

4.4. Target groups and messages

The audience of NEANIAS communication activities includes both specific groups and the general public (including individuals and media). The Open Call focused on scientific and professional communities actively contributed to the technological, procedural, strategic, and business development of EOSC. In this context, the main target groups for the Open Call have been:

- **Research space:** scientists and research centers oriented to the exploitation of the aerospace environment.
- **Research atmospheric:** scientists and research centers oriented to the investigation and exploitation of the earth's atmosphere.
- **Research underwater:** scientists and research centers oriented to the investigation and exploitation of the seabed.
- **Business profile:** companies related to the exploitation or development of services in the three project fields (space, atmospheric and underwater).
- **ICT sector:** companies and organizations in the ICT sector that can offer services or solutions to the research ecosystem in the three environments of the NEANIAS Project.
- **European research:** European research and development ecosystem, especially that related to European projects and the EOSC ecosystem.
- **Academia:** the European research and development fabric basically conveyed through universities and R&D centers.
- **General profile:** the NEANIAS Project Open Call was also open to the general public and, in particular, to fans of technology and the study of the space, atmospheric and underwater environments.

The messages that have been transmitted have been modulated with the evolution of the call and development process of the Open Call. In the first place, the announcement of the Open Call was announced: when it was planned, to whom it was addressed and what were the expected results. Subsequently, the Webinar was announced and disseminated, as a didactic tool of the Open Call process: what were the technical advantages of the services offered by the NEANIAS Project, how would the selection of participants be carried out, resolution of doubts or questions from the participants, etc. The results of the Open Call have finally been communicated.

4.5. Outreach in terms of statistics

As KPIs for the success of the Open Call communication process, the monitoring indices of the different channels used are proposed. Specifically, we can indicate that the messages referring to the Open Call have had the following follow-up:

- **Website:** Open Call contents have had more than 8,000 visits.
- **Twitter:** 13 tweets particularly dedicated to the Open Call that got more than 21,000 impressions and more than 750 engagements. The number of impressions is outstanding; as a reference, the expected number of impressions for the whole project during all its life is 30,000. In addition, from NEANIAS account we interacted, quoted, commented, promoted, and forwarded many tweets produced from other accounts (other projects, followers, or accounts interested in the Open Call).
- **Facebook:** 8 posts generated by the NEANIAS Project with more than 2,100 people reached and more than 200 engagements together. As before, from NEANIAS Facebook account we interacted and engaged any comment from external accounts related to the Open Call.
- **YouTube:** the NEANIAS Project uploaded a video with 170 views.

Additionally, number of people directly contacted: +200 and distribution groups used: 15.

5. Communication Activities on Thematic Levels

5.1. Underwater Thematic Area

The NEANIAS Underwater sector provides three thematic tools related to a) bathymetric data processing, b) underwater photogrammetry, and c) seabed classification derived from multispectral multibeam data. Therefore, the NEANIAS underwater group has circulated the Open Call to communities associated with the marine environment, such as but not limited to:

1. Geologists, marine geologists,
2. Oceanographers,
3. Marine Biologists,
4. Coastal engineers,
5. Maritime Archaeologists,

Moreover, potentially interested SMEs involved in offshore construction and energy have also been targeted.

The NEANIAS Underwater services were presented during the Open Call Webinar held on 17th March 2021. The dissemination and advertisement of the Open Call have been performed systematically through two channels: a) mailing lists and b) social media. Informative emails have been distributed throughout a targeted mailing list compiled from researchers, students, and business partners that would potentially participate in the Open Call. Dedicated meetings were further held for those interested in the Open Call, in order to clarify technical issues and data handling. Moreover, the Open Call was promoted through social media in English and Greek. The event was hosted to the NEANIAS social media channels Facebook and Twitter, where underwater services were demonstrated. Additionally, the work package leader, the service providers, and the end-users of the underwater sector posted the event in their personal accounts and relevant groups.

5.2. Atmospheric Thematic Area

The NEANIAS Atmospheric sector has communicated the Open Call opportunities toward the three target scientific communities, Atmospheric scientists concerned with climate change, Geoscientists concerned with prediction of seismic activity and land stress from emission of certain gases prior to an earthquake and finally the urban pollution scientists concerned with the forecasting of atmospheric pollution in urban environments. These opportunities were also directed toward potentially interested SMEs and business activities, related to High-Performance Computing, Cloud technologies and Artificial Intelligence-based solutions. Furthermore, potential scientific and business collaborators have been also contacted for possible synergies with the other Thematic areas of NEANIAS i.e., Space and Underwater.

NEANIAS Space services were presented during the Open Call webinar organized by the NEANIAS WP5 on 17th March 2021. The announcement and dissemination of the

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Open Call was managed primarily through two channels: mailing lists and social media. General informative mails were sent to selected mailing lists from a number of European research institutions and business partners, in order to engage potential applicants. Additionally, dedicated meetings were also planned with those who expressed their interest in the Call, to discuss the details regarding the NEANIAS Space offerings, in terms of provided services, data handling and expert support.

Besides, a considerable dissemination effort was made in social media to reach as many users as possible and generate interest within the target communities. In particular, the NEANIAS “Atmosphere team and services” were showcased via the official NEANIAS social media channels and also via the personal accounts of the Atmospheric services providers, providing for example raw data for the flux densities calculations of greenhouse gases. Two sample messages have been proposed:

- *Are you conducting research in Climate Change? Would you like to exploit tools and services for the Advanced Determination of greenhouse gases fluxes, Deep understanding of seismic activity prediction and forecasting urban atmospheric pollution? Apply to our Open Call until the 9th April and let's work together on your project with NEANIAS experts.*
- *Would you like to exploit NEANIAS services described above? Are you working in the areas of scientific or business areas described above and would like to boost your projects in collaboration with NEANIAS Experts? Do not lose this unique opportunity and apply to our Open Call.*

5.3. Space Thematic Area

The NEANIAS Space sector has communicated the Open Call opportunities toward the two target scientific communities, Astrophysics and Planetary Science, as well as toward potentially interested SMEs and business activities, related to different sectors, including Space Industry, High-Performance Computing, Cloud technologies and Artificial Intelligence-based solutions. Furthermore, potential scientific and business collaborators have been also contacted for possible synergies with the other Thematic areas of NEANIAS i.e., Atmospheric and Underwater.

NEANIAS Space services were presented during the Open Call webinar organized by the NEANIAS WP5 on 17th March 2021. The announcement and dissemination of the Open Call was managed primarily through two channels: mailing lists and social media. General informative mails were sent to selected mailing lists from a number of European research institutions and business partners, in order to engage potential applicants. The mailing lists are collected on the project repository; additionally, dedicated meetings were also planned with those who expressed their interest in the Call, to discuss the details regarding the NEANIAS Space offerings, in terms of provided services, data handling and expert support.

Besides, a considerable dissemination effort was made in social media to reach as many users as possible and generate interest within the target communities. In particular, the

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

NEANIAS Space team and services were showcased via the official NEANIAS social media channels, in English and in Italian languages, and also via the personal accounts of the Space services providers (see e.g. https://twitter.com/eva_sciacca83/status/1369317703702482956), providing exemplificative pictures of the Space services and descriptions on the innovative impact they could have for potential applicants. Two sample messages have been proposed:

- *Are you conducting research in Astrophysics or Planetary Science? Would you like to exploit tools and services for Advanced Visualization, Maps Processing and Deep Learning models for developing your innovative ideas? Apply to our Open Call until the 9th April and let's work together on your project with NEANIAS experts.*
- *Would you like to exploit NEANIAS services for the Exploration of Mars or the ViaLactea to develop your innovative ideas? Are you working in the areas of Scientific Visualization, Image Processing or Deep Learning and you would like to boost your projects in collaboration with NEANIAS Experts? Do not lose this unique opportunity and apply to our Open Call.*

6. The Submission and Evaluation Process

6.1. The main steps of the process

The evaluation process consisted of 3 main parts, the

1. Submission of the Application, which had a deadline of 9 April.
2. The Evaluation process, consisting of two rounds: the first round, focusing on the evaluation of the applications, and the second round, when the evaluation is based on interviews with the assigned NEANIAS experts.
3. The third phase is focusing on selection, when the open call winners are selected, and the NEANIAS services are assigned.

Submission: the submission of the application was a very simple process, by filling out a short google form. In the submission form we asked general questions about the project of the applicant. In their answers the applicants had to focus on how they plan to utilise NEANIAS services, and what added values NEANIAS experts might provide for them. The NEANIAS experts asked the applicants explicitly to be as concise as possible, by keeping the character limits, as additional characters added against the character limits were not taken into consideration. In the first stage of the submission process, did not ask the applicants to submit any supporting documents.

6.2. The first round of evaluation

As a result of the **intense communication campaign**, and individual discussions with potential applicants, altogether 19 eligible applications arrived (1 more application was submitted late per email, and 1 application neither indicate his clear interest in NEANIAS services nor indicated the thematic sector he belongs to:

Table 3: The Number of Applications per Thematic Sector – First round of Open Call

Thematic sector	No. of Applications
Atmospheric	5
Space	7
Underwater	7
Sum	19

Evaluation: In the first round of the evaluation, the NEANIAS experts created a first evaluation of the applications and they checked if the project fits into the scope of NEANIAS. They were informed and requested to participate at an online interview prepared with NEANIAS experts. The selected seven applicants of the first round are detailed in table 4.

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Table 4: List of applicants – selected in the first round

Country	City	Name of startup/SME/Research institute or Name of Team Members	Thematic Area
Germany	Cologne	NeutronStar Systems UG	Space
Greece	Athens	Nikolaos Tsitomeneas	Space
Portugal	Coimbra	Our Watch Leads - OWL, Lda	Atmospheric
Sweden	Domsjö	Dynamic Genesis (startup)	Atmospheric
Greece	Athens	Sotiria	Underwater
Greece	Thessaloniki	EnaliaTec	Underwater
Hungary	Budapest	GEOInsight Ltd.	Space

The list of other applicants, who submitted their application, but they were not selected in the first round of evaluation is detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: List of applicants - not selected in the first round

Country	Name of startup/SME/Research institute or Name of Team Members	Thematic Area
Greece	Agricultural University of Athens(AUA)	Atmospheric
Italy	University of Milano-Bicocca	Underwater
Hungary	Hastlayer by Lombiq Technologies	Space
Romania	Beia Consult International	Atmospheric
Greece	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens - Faculty of Geology and Geoenvironment	Underwater
Germany	NeutronStar Systems UG	Space

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Spain	Relief Applications	Space
Italy	TerraMap (Group of innovators: Giuseppe Garofalo & Luca Sciacca)	Atmospheric
Sweden	AgroForestry	Underwater
Greece	-	Underwater
Greece	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Underwater
Hungary	GEOInsight Ltd.	Space

The first round of selection of applications was concluded on April 27th, 2021, 16:00 CEST, in the frame of the Open Call Evaluation Board meeting. In the next round, **the applicants were invited for an interview with the assigned NEANIAS experts** to provide further information about their project and discuss about the possible collaboration opportunities. The final selection of the winners took place on May 21st, then the collaboration started between the selected applicants and the NEANIAS experts.

6.3. The second round of evaluation and selection criteria

In the second round of the evaluation, during the interview NEANIAS technical and business experts asked more details about the project, and checked its viability, feasibility, sustainability and fit into NEANIAS objectives. At this stage, NEANIAS experts had the chance to request further supporting documents about the project to check any additional technical details.

The applications must meet both business and technical criteria, described in Table6 and Table7:

Table 6: Business criteria of Open Call applicant's evaluation

Main criteria	Details of the criteria
Added value for NEANIAS Partners	The project might provide additional business opportunities to NEANIAS partners and increase the value of NEANIAS services
Corporate background	Corporate background (SM presence, Website) - innomine

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Business potential	The project has a clear business potential, and NEANIAS can increase that with the services provided
---------------------------	--

Table 7: Technical criteria of Open Call applicant's evaluation

Main criteria	Details of the criteria
Novelty	By using one or more services of the NEANIAS project (please check the service list of NEANIAS), a significant impact can be made and achieved on your project in terms of novelty.
Exclusivity	The project can utilise NEANIAS services, which provide an answer to research needs, which would otherwise not be available by using internal competencies.
Technical excellence and industrial relevance	The proposed project provides technical excellence, as by developing a new product and/or service, a novel, innovative technology/service can be developed. The developed product has a novelty and relevance in terms of added value in the given industry.
Feasibility, Sustainability, and Viability	The proposed solution is using NEANIAS services for a limited period, and by utilising these services the added value of NEANIAS is straightforward, and quantifiable metrics are defined.

The recordings of the interviews and the attendance sheets are uploaded to NEANIAS SharePoint, in the *WP5 folder/Open Call/1st Open Call – Interviews/Recordings* folder.

Selection: based on the evaluation of experts, each applicant received an individual score, and they received feedback about the result of their application within one month of the interview.

The final, three projects were selected by the Open Call Evaluation Board, through two rounds of evaluation, after each expert filled in the scoring sheet of each individual application. Through the Evaluation Board Meetings, taking place on May 21st 2021, and on the May 28th, 2021, the experts discussed about the potential opportunities and added values for NEANIAS on working together with each application. As a result of the two-round selection, the NEANIAS Evaluation Board and NEANIAS experts analysed both the technical and the business aspects of each applicant, and made sure, that the selected winners will integrate the services of NEANIAS, both by building on business and technological perspectives.

The winners of the First Open Call, and the NEANIAS services to be provided:

Table 8: The winners of the First Open Call

Name of Applicant	Thematic Sector	Country
OWL LDA	Atmospheric	Portugal
GEOInsight Ltd.	Space	Hungary
EnaliaTec	Underwater	Greece

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

7. Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable provided an overview of the first Open Call organised in the NEANIAS project. This first open call had the target to collect at least 15 applicants including the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space thematic fields. Even though the topic of this Open Call and the target audience was rather narrow and specific, 19 valid, and high-quality applications were collected as a result of the call. The selected projects will therefore have a chance to utilise and integrate the services of NEANIAS to use it in developing their current services and products.

The aim of this Open Call was to support NEANIAS by finding relevant companies, who could utilise, test, and integrate the services of NEANIAS. As a result of the intense communication campaign, targeted messages and the intense collaboration and work on mobilising the network of thematic experts a high number of applications was collected.

After the selection procedure, the successful three projects of the first open call will start working with NEANIAS experts of the selected thematic fields of Underwater, Atmospheric or Space research. After signing an NDA, and creating a concise project abstract, where the clear goals of the project are defined; the project implementation starts. The projects will receive technical and business-related support in the POC implementation phase, at least during a three-months period. This period will be followed by a one-week collaboration with NEANIAS experts on evaluating the POC, and creating the closing report, where the status of development and the added values of NEANIAS will be described. The projects might receive additional support from NEANIAS experts to implement their business cases, which can be further negotiated and agreed between the projects and NEANIAS experts.

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

8. Appendixes

8.1. Appendix 1: NEANIAS posts

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Social Media Posts + Design/ Images:

English Version:

FREE WEBINAR:

LAST CHANCE TO REGISTER - FREE WEBINAR: <https://bit.ly/3vbGeW2>

#atmospheric #underwater #space #research #project #webinar #freewebinar

1st

NEANIAS Open Call

Do not miss our Webinar on the 17 March 2021!

”

Neanias is an excellent project, that draws an ambitious path dedicated to **Prototyping New Innovative Services in the Underwater, Atmospheric, and Space research** thematic areas, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

Dr. Gábor Vicze
CEO
Innomine Group Ltd.

 Neanias receives funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 863448

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

8.2. Appendix 2: List of direct mail contacts

List of international student networks

Group	Country	Link, etc.
COST Network	All	
Blue Cloud and Trust IT Network	Europe	
DIH Network	Europe	
IDS Hungary	Hungary	http://idsa.hu/?fbclid=IwAR2xV6OdAgbkQk8Ez1cVUHLKDSz5IZvs561_7QhWdCk2jg7sbv5LOU6Rkg
Aircargochallenge competition group	Germany	https://akamodell-muenchen.de/en/projekte/
Thalia Study association	The Netherlands	https://thalia.nu/contact
Marie Curie A.	The Netherlands	https://marie-curie.nl/page/show/2
Umbrella Org. For Students assoc.	Europe	http://www.sofv.nl/
NHSV	The Netherlands	https://nshv.nl/contact/
ESN Rotterdam	The Netherlands	https://esn-rotterdam.nl/
EURODOC	Europe	http://www.eurodoc.net/eurodoc/eurodoc-secretariat
European University Association	Europe	https://eua.eu/
Max Planck - Quantum Optics	Europe	https://www.mpg.mpg.de/4744813/research_groups
		https://eua-cde.org/contact.html
		https://www.eui.eu/About/Contacts
		https://welcome-solutions.com/contact/
		https://stipendiat.no/about/board/
		https://www.dtu.dk/english/education/student-guide/student-life/clubs-and-associations/phd-association
		https://www.euro-online.org/web/pages/1450/contact
		https://www.iau-aiu.net/PARTNERSHIPS
		https://www.euroseas.org/contact/
		https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/stor-i/about-us/#d.en.395534
		https://www.eurashe.eu/
International Association of Universities	International association	https://www.iau-aiu.net/Secretariat
Academic Cooperation Association	International association	https://aca-secretariat.be/
L'Agence Universitaire de la Francophonie	International association	https://www.auf.org/a-propos/contact/
Mediterranean Universities Union	International association	https://www.uni-med.net/staff/
Balkan Universities Association	International association	http://www.baunas.org/
HSE	International association	https://www.hse.ru/en/info/
Worldwide Universities Network (WUN)	International association	https://www.wun.ac.uk/
Matariki Network of Universities, Durban	International association	https://www.matarikinetwerk.org/about/contact/
	International association	https://universitas21.com/what-we-do/about-us/management-team
European University Association	European Association	https://eua.eu/contact.html
Coimbra Group	European Association	https://www.coimbra-group.eu/contact/
	European Association	https://www.eaie.org/about-eaie/contact.html
	European Association	https://www.eucor-uni.org/nous-connaître/contact/
	University	https://www.eucor-uni.org/nous-connaître/contact/
	European Association	https://europaeum.org/people/
		https://idealeague.org/about/
		https://www.leru.org/about-leru#members

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

List of Smart City and air quality monitoring groups

Relevance	Websites
Experimental urban me	https://arrayofthings.github.io/index.html
Smart street lighting as a platform	https://www.smartcitylab.com/blog/urban-environment/lighting-the-road-to-smart-cities-and-
Smart city	https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/ecologiaurbana/en/about-us
Smart city	https://www.barcelona.cat/en/getinvolved
Smart city	https://www.luclassociation.org/map-city/copenhagen-2/
Smart city	https://www.smart-energy.com/industry-sectors/policy-
Smart city	https://smartcitysweden.com/contact/
Smart city	https://eu.smartcitiescouncil.com/contact-us-eu
Smart city	https://eu.smartcitiescouncil.com/contact-us-eu
Smart city	https://www.smart-city.uliege.be/cms/c_5216187/en/smartcity-the-institute
Smart city	http://smartcity.csr.unibo.it/contacts/
Smart city	https://www.smart-circle.org/portfolios/cleverciti-systems/
Smart city	http://www.cityzen-smartcity.eu/home/contacts/
Smart city	https://www.tmapy.com/smartcity
Smart city	https://www.wur.nl/en/Persons/Marian-dr.ir.-M-Marian-Stuiver.htm
Smart city	http://www.bizertesmartcity.com/en/
Smart city	https://www.vaisala.com/en/industries-applications/urban-environment
Smart city	https://hub.beesmart.city/en/our-mission-and-team
Smart city	https://smartcitygovernance.eu/?page_id=124
Smart city	http://www.cityzen-smartcity.eu/home/contacts/
Smart city	https://irissmartcities.eu/
	https://smartdublin.ie/about/
Odour processing	https://www.ortelium.com/client-solutions/animal-processing
Airport air monitoring	https://www.opsis.se/en/Applications/Ambient-Air-Quality-Monitoring/Airport-Monitoring
Hurricane prevention	https://www.sintef.no/en/latest-news/preventing-hurricanes-using-air-bubbles/
Smart city	http://organicity.eu/
Air quality measurement	https://www.vaisala.com/en/lp/contact-form/contact-us?field_countries_value=HU&field_business_areas_target_id=All
Air quality measurement	https://www.vaisala.com/sites/default/files/documents/AQ-for-Ports-Brochure-B211778EN.pdf
smart city	http://human.co/
	https://www.mapbox.com/industries/agriculture
smart city	https://looperproject.eu/about/contact/

Hungarian direct mail contacts

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Name of institution
Admatis Kft.
Amnis KFT.
BME
Corvinus University Of Budapest
EnviroInvest Zrt
HUNSPACE - Hungarian Space Cluster
Lombiq Technologies
Matthias Corvinus Collegium
Metropolitan University
Óbuda University
Pécsi Tudományegyetem
Pulinspace
CarpathiaSat
Softflow
StartIT UP
Széchenyi István University Győr
Tempus Foundation

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

8.3. Appendix 3: SM groups with outreach targeted by innomine

Linkedin groups with outreach

LINKEDIN Group	Link	Status	Date	# of members
International Society of Intelligent Unmanned System	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4808262/	posted	April 6th	549
The Society for Underwater Technology (SUT)	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2440524/	posted x2	April 6th	3 615
National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/833297/	requested to join		929
Institute for Marine and Atmospheric research Utrecht (IMAU)	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3956678/			266
Tech Experts - Security, Software, Cloud, IoT, Robotics, A.I., Finance, Health, Space & Science	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/957667/	posted		55 585
Future Engineers Innovators & Innovations Science Technology Art Automotive Engineer Aerospace Space	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3698699/	Requested to join	April 6th	2 663
Space Science and Astrophysics	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/6564084/	Requested to join		56
Women In Aerospace Europe	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2594115/	Requested to join		972
EU Sustainability Public Affairs (Brussels)	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13748000/	posted x2	April 6th	541
Horizon2020 - H2020 - HorizonEurope	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3172785/	posted x2	April 6th	1 634

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Facebook groups with outreach targeted by Innomine

FACEBOOK Group	Link	Status	Date	# of members
Horizon 2020, EU Funding & Framework Programme for Research & Innovation	https://www.facebook.com/groups/horizon2020	posted x2	April 6th	8 500
Underwater Robotic Research Group (URRG)	https://www.facebook.com/URRGLAB	Can't post publically		356
Space Research	https://www.facebook.com/Space-Research-1867894973475478	posted		1 791
Space Research 2	https://www.facebook.com/Space-Research-190096361018500	inactive		688
Space EU	https://www.facebook.com/spaceEUorg	can't post publically		2 799
National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)	https://www.facebook.com/UKAtmosScience	posted		1 786
UTeM Underwater Technology Research Group (UTeRG)	https://www.facebook.com/groups/uterg	can't post publically		179
HORIZON: the EU Research & Innovation magazine	https://www.facebook.com/horizon.magazine.eu	can't post publically		43 751
ISRO Science and Technology	https://www.facebook.com/groups/448319368602038	posted x2	april 6th	168.5K
UKM Atmospheric Chemistry and Air Pollution Research Group	https://www.facebook.com/UKMAtmosphere	can't post publically		820
UTRtek - Underwater Technical Research Tek Diving	https://www.facebook.com/groups/106897941991	posted x2	april 6th	807
Foundation for Underwater Research and Education	https://www.facebook.com/Foundation-for-Underwater-Research-and-Education-358790251332752	posted		118
SPC Underwater Research Society (SURS)	https://www.facebook.com/groups/SPCUnderwaterResearchSociety	posted	april 6th	192
Smart Cities Trends	https://www.facebook.com/smartcitystrends/	posted x2	april 6th	3,596
Smart Cities	https://www.facebook.com/World.SmartCities	posted		5, 740
ASEAN Smart Cities Network	https://www.facebook.com/groups/2075775515979542	posted		1, 400

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

8.4. Appendix 4: General communication channels of NEANIAS

NEANIAS Website Open Call Page

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS website's Open Call page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the NEANIAS logo, links for HOME, NEWS, ABOUT THE SITE, and CONTACT US, and a search box. Below the navigation bar, a breadcrumb trail indicates the user is on the Home / OPEN CALL page. A left sidebar contains a menu with categories like PROJECT, CONSORTIUM, ORGANIZATION, DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS, EVENTS & ACTIVITIES, and OPEN CALL. The main content area features a large banner for the '1st NEANIAS Open Call' with a globe image and a starburst indicating an application deadline of 9 April 2021. Below the banner, there are sections for 'Open Call' (describing the program), 'All the details' (listing key information points), 'Even more details' (mentioning a video presentation), 'Do you want us to present the Open Call to you?' (inviting to a webinar), and 'Apply Now?' (providing instructions and a link to the application form).

Open Call

Apply for our unique program to validate your innovative idea and boost the development with NEANIAS experts for free!

1st NEANIAS Open Call
Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Sciences in the European Open Science Cloud

Application deadline: 9 April 2021

Call for proposals with a deadline of 9 April 2021 opens for companies and teams of individual researchers to utilise the services developed within the NEANIAS project.

All the details

- What services do we provide for the winners?
- Purpose and background of the Open Call.
- Selection and execution processes.
- Eligibility criteria and Conditions.

Even more details

Do not miss this video presentation that explains everything you need to know about the Open Call.

Do you want us to present the Open Call to you?

NEANIAS team would like to invite you to an online webinar, taking place on the 17 March, 15:00h CET to present the Open Call. The registration to the webinar is open until March-16, 2021, at noon.

Interesting? Interested? Please, sign up here: [webinar registration form](#). It is free.

Apply Now?

Please follow the instructions and submit your application by clicking on [Open Call Application Form](#).

For additional information on the Open Call, you can also contact us through OpenCall@neanias.eu.
Subscribe to NEANIAS to be updated!

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

8.5. Appendix 5: Banner of the Open Call

8.6. Appendix 6: Questions of the Application Form

Name
Surname
Email Address
Gender
Telephone No.
City
Name of your startup/SME/Research institute or Name of Team Members
Year of foundation
Country
Do you have experience with H2020 projects?
Turnover in the last financial year
Headcount in the last financial year
Have you received investment so far? If so, what is the volume?*
Website
Twitter - Organisation*
Facebook - Organization*
LinkedIn - Team member/Company*
Please introduce your activity (max 2000 characters)
Which NEANIAS services you intend to use?
What added values do you expect from NEANIAS? (max 1000 characters)

8.7. Appendix 7: Main criteria for the Scoring of Applications

1: Do NOT meet the criteria, 10: Perfectly MEET the criteria
Evaluation criteria - Business aspects - WP5/WP9
The project might provide additional business opportunities to NEANIAS partners and increase the value of NEANIAS services?
Corporate background: Please ask about the Team and the competencies. Do they have anyone with a corporate, or business background?
The project has a clear business potential, and NEANIAS can increase that with the services provided
Evaluation criteria - Technology aspects - WP2/WP3/WP4 Partners
Novelty: By using one or more services of the NEANIAS project, a significant impact can be achieved in terms of the novelty of the developed product, or service described in the application form.
Exclusivity: The project described in the application, can utilise novel NEANIAS services, which provide a solution on their research needs, which would otherwise not available for them by using their internal competencies.
Technical excellence and industrial relevance: The proposed project provide technical excellence, as by developing a new product and/or service, a novel, innovative technology/service can be developed.
Realistic: The proposed solution is using NEANIAS services for a limited period (ideally 3 month) time, and by utilising these services the added value of NEANIAS is straightforward, and quantifiable metrics are defined.

8.8. Appendix 8: Interview dates and evaluators - Second round of selection

A-2
Spyridon Rapsomanikis
Theodoros Rokkas/Ioannis Neokosmidis
Simone Mantovani

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

6 May, 9 am CEST

A-5
Spyridon Rapsomanikis
Ricardo Vitorino
Simone Mantovani
Theodoros Rokkas/loannis Neokosmidis
10 May, 12:00 CEST

S-1
Simone Mantovani
Ricardo Vitorino
Angelo Pio
Theodoros Rokkas/loannis Neokosmidis
6 May, 9 am CEST

S-5
Simone Mantovani
Theodoros Rokkas/loannis Neokosmidis
Angelo Pio/Filomena
Eva Sciacca
12 May, 10:00 CEST

S-7
Simone Mantovani
Filomena Solitro
Theodoros Rokkas/loannis Neokosmidis
Eva Sciacca
12 May 11:00 CEST

U-5
Evi Nomikou
Paul.Wintersteller
Stergios Kokorotsikos
Theodoros Rokkas/loannis Neokosmidis
6 May, 10:00 CEST

U-7
Evi Nomikou
Paul.Wintersteller
Konstantinos Karantzas
Kalliopi Baika

Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered

Ioannis Neokosmidis/Katalin Kovács

11 May 10:00 CEST
